

660 **Table 1 – Scenarios under assessment.**

Scenario	0	1	2A	2B	2C
Preliminary treatment	Degritting and degreasing; Initial pumping	Degritting and degreasing; Initial pumping	Degritting and degreasing; Initial pumping	Degritting and degreasing; Initial pumping	Degritting and degreasing; Initial pumping
Primary treatment	Primary sedimentation	Primary sedimentation	Primary sedimentation	Chemical assisted primary sedimentation (CAPS)	Rotating belt screen (RBS)
Secondary treatment	Activated sludge system (Schreiber process integrated with chemical P precipitation)	Activated sludge system (Schreiber process integrated with chemical P precipitation)	Activated sludge system (Schreiber process integrated with chemical P precipitation)	Activated sludge system (Schreiber process integrated with chemical P precipitation)	Activated sludge system (Schreiber process integrated with chemical P precipitation)
Sludge treatment	Gravity Thickening; Anaerobic digestion; Sludge dewatering; Composting; Biosolids application to agriculture	Gravity Thickening; Anaerobic digestion; Sludge dewatering; Composting; Biosolids application to agriculture	Dynamic thickening; Anaerobic digestion; Sludge dewatering; Composting; Biosolids application to agriculture	Anaerobic digestion; Sludge dewatering; Composting; Biosolids application to agriculture	Anaerobic digestion; Sludge dewatering; Composting; Biosolids application to agriculture
Return liquor treatment	-	SCENA	SCENA ^a	SCENA ^a	SCENA ^a
Odour treatment	Bio-filter	Bio-filter	Bio-filter	Bio-filter	Bio-filter

661 ^a SCENA system has been modelled based on pilot scale results (Renzi et al. 2015) (see section B of supplementary
662 file)

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674 **Table 2 – Nitrogen and phosphorus mass balance.**

Plant section		Scenario 0		Scenario 1		Scenario 2A		Scenario 2B		Scenario 2C	
		Main line	Main line	Side stream							
Nitrogen mass balance											
N influent load	kgN/d	392.2	391.3	36.23	391.3	30.87	391.3	30.68	391.3	30.68	
N ₂ O-N to air	kgN/d	4.55	2.380	0.516	2.141	0.540	2.197	0.611	2.197	0.611	
N ₂ -N to air	kgN/d	243.5	241.4	19.56	242.5	25.71	244.0	25.05	244.0	25.05	
N in the effluent	kgN/d	98.70	75.95	14.67	70.98	3.156	71.76	3.630	71.76	3.630	
N availability in biosolids	%	50.00	50.00	50.00	50.00	50.00	50.00	50.00	50.00	50.00	
N recovered that offsets fertilizer	kgN/d	12.55	13.11	0.330	15.56	0.341	15.06	0.500	15.94	0.341	
NO ₃ -N to water due to land application	kgN/d	21.08	20.40	0.663	23.95	0.844	24.25	0.805	22.82	0.805	
N ₂ O-N to air due to land application	kgN/d	0.697	0.694	0.007	0.818	0.028	0.741	0.027	0.803	0.027	
NH ₃ -N to air due to land application	kgN/d	2.225	2.235	0.070	2.637	0.092	2.608	0.087	2.608	0.087	
Phosphorus mass balance											
P influent load	kgP/d	44.15	44.32	2.898	44.32	1.985	44.32	1.976	44.32	1.976	
P in the effluent	kgP/d	18.98	18.52	2.798	18.33	0.526	12.35	0.605	18.53	0.605	
P availability in biosolids	%	56.36	59.58	100.0	68.75	100.0	9.560	100.0	65.05	100.0	
P recovered that offsets fertilizer	kgP/d	14.75	15.18	0.128	17.55	0.782	3.575	0.816	16.67	0.816	
PO ₄ -P to water due to biosolids application	kgP/d	0.672	0.653	0.007	0.649	0.041	0.961	0.043	0.652	0.043	

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682 **Table 3 - Economic analysis for each scenario (Costs are reported in EURO for the removal of 1 kg of**
683 **PO₄³⁻ eq.).**

Scenario	Construction	Electricity	Chemicals	Labour	Sludge composting	Total cost
Scenario 0	0.00	2.73	0.41	0.86	1.53	5.52
Scenario 1	0.16	2.45	0.38	0.86	1.50	5.35
Scenario 2A	0.21	2.39	0.35	0.85	1.43	5.23
Scenario 2B	0.15	2.08	1.09	0.80	1.64	5.75
Scenario 2C	0.29	2.29	0.41	0.85	1.66	5.50

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 698 **Fig. 1 – Flow diagram of the SCENA system implemented at the Carbonera WWTP (sc. 1). Solid lines show flow**
 699 **of water, dashed lines show sludge or solid flow and dotted lines show biogas flow. In sc. 0, the anaerobic**
 700 **supernatant is recycled to the head of the plant without further treatment. Note: WAS = waste activated**
 701 **sludge; GST = gravitational sludge thickener; SBFR = sequencing batch fermentation reactor; AD = anaerobic**
 702 **digester; VFAs = volatile fatty acids; scSBR = short-cut sequencing batch reactor.**

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 713 **Fig. 2 - Comparison of freshwater eutrophication (a) and marine freshwater potential (b) for**
 714 **treatment configurations under study.**

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728 **Fig. 3 - Comparison of global warming potential for treatment configurations under study.**

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 749 **Fig. 4 - Comparison of human toxicity (a) and terrestrial ecotoxicity (b) for treatment configurations**
 750 **under study.**

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 763 **Fig. 5 - Comparison of ozone depletion (a), photochemical oxidant formation (b), particular matter**
 764 **formation (c), and terrestrial acidification for treatment configurations under study.**

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Fig. 6 - Monte Carlo simulation results of characterized LCIA comparison.